

SYNTHESIS OF PIPERIDINE DERIVATIVES. PART I. SUBSTITUTED N-METHYL-4-PIPERIDOLS

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Four different diethyl 1-methyl-2 : 6-diphenyl-4-alkyl (or aryl)-4-oxypiperidine-3 : 5-dicarboxylic esters have been synthesised by the action of the appropriate alkyl or aryl magnesium halide on diethyl 1-methyl-2 : 6-diphenyl-4-piperidone-3 : 5-dicarboxylate.

Considerable effort has been made in recent years for the synthesis of analgesics which do not possess the undesirable after-effects produced by morphine and atropine viz. the dryness of the mouth, increased heart-beat and blood-pressure and antagonisation of the acetylcholine set free at the nerve endings and lastly, drug addiction. Eisleb and Schaumann (*Deut. Med. Wochr.*, 1939, 65, 967 ; *Ber.*, 1941, 74, 1433) deserve the credit of preparing for the first time a compound "Dolantin" with such properties, which has found universal and extensive application. Dolantin is the hydrochloride of pethidine (ethyl 1-methyl-4-phenylpiperidine-4-carboxylate) (I). Synthesis of pethidine has also been later achieved by Bergel, Morrison and Rinderknecht (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 267) and by Walton and Green (*ibid.*, 1945, 316). This compound is a substituted piperidine.

The present work was undertaken with a view to preparing other substituted piperidines and to examine them for possible analgesic and antispasmodic properties.

The pharmacological interest attaching to piperidine derivatives has led several workers to investigate methods of synthesising compounds of this series. Cook and Barr (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 438) obtained N-alkyl-substituted piperidines by the hydrogenation of γ -cyano esters in alcoholic solution with copper chromite. Koelsch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2093, 2458, 2459, 2460) has also effected a number of intermediate preparations of N-alkyl 4-piperidones. Cook and Reed (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 399) obtained 4-piperidone derivatives from bis- γ -cyanoethyl-methylamine which were later converted into more complex heterocyclic systems. Anker, Cook and Heilbron (*ibid.*, 1945, 917) prepared a N-phenyl analogue of Dolantin and other analogous compounds with oxygenated groupings in the N-phenyl residue. Cook and Anker (*ibid.*, 1946, 58) have further extended this work to the synthesis of pyridocoumarins and dimethylpyran derivatives.

A very simple method for the preparation of compounds of Pethidine type has been developed by the present authors. It consists of the action of different alkyl and aryl magnesium halides on substituted γ -piperidones, obtained by the Mannich reaction. In this paper the synthesis of four different diethyl 1-methyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-alkyl (or aryl)-4-oxypiperidine-3:5-dicarboxylates is described. They have been obtained by the action of the appropriate alkyl (or aryl) magnesium halides on diethyl 1-methyl-2:6-diphenylpiperidone-3:5-dicarboxylate (II).

The results of the investigation of the physiological properties of these compounds will be communicated later.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diethyl 1-methyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-piperidone-3:5-dicarboxylate (II) was prepared essentially by the method of Petrenko-Kritschenko and Lewin (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2884; 1909, 42, 3684) but with modifications which led to easier isolation of the end product.

To a mixture of ethyl acetone dicarboxylate (13.5 g., 0.67 mole) and benzaldehyde (14 g., 0.137 mole), cooled in ice, were added at an interval of about 15 minutes, 15 c. c. of a 33% ice-cold alcoholic solution of methylamine (4 g., 0.135 mole) and left overnight in the refrigerator. After twelve hours' standing at room temperature, it was diluted with alcohol (1:1) and saturated with hydrochloric acid gas under cooling. The precipitated hydrochloride of the piperidone (II) was collected, washed with ice-cold alcohol and covered with an excess of ammonia. Next day the liberated piperidone (II) was filtered off, dried and recrystallised from hot alcohol, m. p. 86°. yield 49%; hydrochloride, m. p. 196°.

Diethyl 1-Methyl-2:6-diphenyl-4-ethyl-4-oxypiperidine-3:5-dicarboxylate (III).—The Grignard reagent from ethyl iodide (1.2 g., 0.0075 mole) and magnesium (0.18 g., 0.0075 mole) was prepared as usual in 25 c. c. anhydrous ether in a three-necked flask fitted with a reflux condenser, a mechanical stirrer and a

dropping funnel, nitrogen being admitted through a side tube in the flask. After 10 minutes' cooling in ice, vacuum dried piperidone (II, 3.1 g., 0.0075 mole), dissolved in 30 c. c. of dry ether was added in rapid drops from the dropping funnel. A pale yellow precipitate separated immediately and coated the sides of the flask. After half an hour's refluxing of the ether on a water-bath, the contents were poured on to crushed ice and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid (Congo red). The ethereal layer was decanted off and the precipitate collected, and recrystallised from boiling alcohol in small white needles, m.p. 163°, yield 3 g. (90% of theory). It is also soluble in chloroform. (Found : N, 2.82. $C_{26}H_{33}O_3N$ requires N, 3.19 per cent).

The ethereal layer on evaporation after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate left no residue.

Diethyl 1-methyl-2 : 6-diphenyl-4-n-propyl-4-oxypiperidine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate (IV) was obtained by the action of *n*-propyl magnesium bromide (from Mg, 0.18 g., 0.0075 mole and *n*-propyl bromide, 1 g., 0.0075 mole in 25 c.c. dry ether in an atmosphere of nitrogen) on piperidone (II, 3 g., 0.0075 mole), dissolved in dry ether, as described under compound (III) and recrystallised from boiling alcohol in small white needles, m.p. 186-87°, yield 3.1 g. (90% of theory). (Found : N, 2.68. $C_{27}H_{35}O_5N$ requires N, 3.09 per cent).

The ethereal layer after drying and evaporation left no residue in this case also.

Diethyl 1-methyl-2 : 6-diphenyl-4-n-butyl-4-oxypiperidine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate (V) was prepared by the action of *n*-butyl magnesium bromide on piperidone (II, 3 g.), dissolved in dry ether, as under (III), and recrystallised from boiling alcohol in small white needles, m. p. 191-92°, yield 3.3 g. (94% of theory). (Found : N, 2.71. $C_{28}H_{37}O_5N$ requires N, 3.00 per cent).

In this case also the ethereal layer on evaporation left no residue.

Diethyl 1-methyl-2 : 6-diphenyl-4-phenyl-4-oxypiperidine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate (VI) was prepared by the action of phenyl magnesium bromide (from 0.36 g. of Mg and 2.4 g. of bromobenzene, in 100 c. c. dry ether in an atmosphere of nitrogen) on piperidone (II, 6 g.), dissolved in dry ether as described under compound (III). A small quantity of diphenyl was also formed and was recovered from the ethereal layer. The precipitate of compound (VI), formed on decomposing the Grignard-complex by sulphuric acid, was therefore washed with 50 c.c. of ether to remove any diphenyl.

The compound (VI) is sparingly soluble in boiling ethyl alcohol and almost insoluble in ether, acetone, chloroform, petroleum ether, benzene and toluene. It was recrystallised from boiling methyl alcohol (30 c.c. methyl alcohol for 1 g. of the compound). It was quite pure when washed once with ether, followed by a small quantity of boiling methyl or ethyl alcohol, m. p. 186°, yield 6.5 g. (90% of theory) (Found : N, 2.63. $C_{30}H_{35}O_5N$ requires N, 2.94 per cent).

